

INTEGRAL METHODS FOR ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS USING SYMBOLIC ALGEBRA

Seichi Nomura
(University of Texas at Arlington, Arlington, Texas 76019 USA)

ABSTRACT

With the help of symbolic algebra software, it is now possible to treat the vast array of problems in composite materials analytically that were done previously via purely numerical methods such as finite element analysis. In this paper, an integral method is presented that takes advantage of symbolic algebra for elastic fields of general composite materials and buckling of composites plates.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, numerical methods particularly exemplified by finite element emerged as indispensable tools to analyze composite materials and numerous problems in composites are solved using these numerical techniques on routine basis.

Meanwhile, the usefulness of symbolic algebra is being recognized among the engineering community and several papers appeared in solid mechanics in recent years. These software programs such as MACSYMA and REDUCE can perform differentiating, integrating or expanding many transcendental functions and manipulating matrix algebra.

In this paper, an implementation of the Galerkin procedure using symbolic algebra software is presented in two branches of the analysis of composite materials. An integral method which has been successfully applied to the analysis of transient heat conduction¹ is adopted and symbolic algebra software, REDUCE², has been used for the analysis.

In the first part, the elastic Green's function for general composites is expressed as a series of eigenfunctions for the corresponding eigenvalue problem. These eigenfunctions are determined by the Galerkin method as a linear combination of shape functions each of which satisfies a homogeneous boundary condition. Stress fields in materials for various boundary conditions (displacement, traction and mixed) can be expressed once the Green's function for the accompanying problem is found.

In the second part, a unified technique to handle composite plates with any given boundary conditions is presented using symbolic algebra software. The lateral displacement in composite plates is expressed as a series of polynomials each of which satisfies the given boundary conditions. Using these techniques, buckling of composite plates with free edges is analyzed.

In both analyses, the obtained expressions are in closed form and unlike purely numerical methods such as finite element or finite difference methods, this method does not require excessive computational time nor huge memory storage.

3-D ELASTICITY

The elastic equilibrium equation for general anisotropic and inhomogeneous composites is expressed as

$$L u_i(\mathbf{r}) + b_i(\mathbf{r}) = 0 \quad (1)$$

where $u_i(\mathbf{r})$ is the displacement field, \mathbf{r} is the (three-dimensional) position vector, $b_i(\mathbf{r})$ is body force and L is a differential operator defined as

$$(L u)_i = (C_{ijkl} u_{k,l})_{,j} \quad (2)$$

where $_{,i}$ denotes the partial derivative with respect to x_i , $C_{ijkl}(\mathbf{r})$ is anisotropic elastic modulus and the repeated index denotes summation. Equation (1) together with appropriate boundary conditions (displacement, traction or mixed) constitute a boundary value problem.

The Green's function for such materials is defined as

$$L g_{km}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') + \delta_{im} \delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}') = 0 \quad (3)$$

with homogeneous boundary conditions.

where δ_{im} is the Kronecker delta and $\delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}')$ is the Dirac delta function.

It can be readily shown that once the Green's function of Eq.(2) is found, the displacement field can be expressed as a boundary integral term plus a convolution integral between the Green's function and the distributed body force³. For example, if the boundary condition is given in terms of the displacement (Dirichlet) as

$$u(\mathbf{r}) = u^A \quad \mathbf{r} \in \text{boundary points} \quad (4)$$

then, the displacement field at any interior point, \mathbf{r} , can be written as

$$u_m(\mathbf{r}) = \int_{\partial\Omega} g_{im,j}(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}') C_{ijkl}(\mathbf{r}') u_k^A(\mathbf{r}') n_l(\mathbf{r}') ds' + \int_{\Omega} g_{mi}(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}') b_i(\mathbf{r}') dr' \quad (5)$$

where Ω is the material domain, $\partial\Omega$ is the material boundary points and \mathbf{n} is a normal vector on the boundary.

The solution to Eq.(3) is assumed to have the following form:

$$g_{im}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') = \sum_a h_i^a(\mathbf{r}') \psi_m^a(\mathbf{r}) \quad (6)$$

where $h_1^a(r')$ is a function of r' to be determined and $\psi_m^a(r)$ is an eigenfunction for the following eigenvalue problem:

$$(L \psi^a)_m = \lambda^a \psi_m^a \quad (7)$$

(no summation over a)

Substitution of Eq.(6) into Eq.(3), multiplying the result by $\psi_m^\beta(r)$ and integrating over r , $h_1^\beta(r')$ yields

$$g_{1m}(r, r') = - \sum_a \frac{1}{\lambda^a} \psi_1^a(r') \psi_m^a(r) \quad (8)$$

Therefore, the Green's function is constructed once the eigenfunction, $\psi_m^a(r)$, is found. Eigenfunctions, $\psi_m(r)$, are assumed to be expanded by a series of trial functions, $f_\beta(r)$, as

$$\psi_k(r) = \sum_\beta c_k^\beta f_\beta(r) \quad (9)$$

where c_k^β 's are coefficients to be determined and $f_\beta(r)$'s are trial shape functions chosen from a complete set of functions that satisfy the homogeneous boundary condition.

Substituting Eq.(9) into Eq.(7), multiplying by $f_\gamma(r)$ and integrating over the entire material points, the following equation is obtained:

$$\sum_\beta A_{mk}^{\beta\gamma} c_k^\beta = \lambda \sum_\beta B^{\beta\gamma} c_m^\beta \quad (10)$$

where

$$A_{mk}^{\beta\gamma} = \int_\Omega (C_{mjkl} f_{\beta,l})_{,j} f_\gamma \, dr \quad (11)$$

and

$$B^{\beta\gamma} = \int_\Omega f_\beta f_\gamma \, dr \quad (12)$$

Components of Eqs.(11) and (12) are evaluated exactly using symbolic algebra software. When there are multiple inclusions (inhomogeneities, fibers, voids...), integral is repeated for each inclusion phase.

COMPOSITE PLATE BUCKLING

A two-dimensional anisotropic composite plate is subject to compressional load. For simplicity, classical laminate theory is adopted here although it is possible to extend to higher order theories. The governing equation for the lateral displacement, w , is expressed in tensorial form as

$$D_{ijkl} w_{,ijkl} = N_{ij} w_{,ij} \quad (13)$$

where the repeated index implies summation over x_1 and x_2 . In Eq.(13), D_{ijkl} 's and N_{ij} 's are components of the anisotropic flexural moduli and stress resultants of the composite defined as

$$D_{ijkl} = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} z^2 C_{ijkl}(z) dz \quad (14)$$

$$N_{ij} = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \sigma_{ij}(z) dz \quad (15)$$

where $C_{ijkl}(z)$ is the (anisotropic) elastic modulus of each lamina and h is the total thickness of the plate.

The solution to Eq.(13) is assumed to be a linear combination of base functions as

$$w(x,y) = \sum_a c_a \psi_a(x,y) \quad (16)$$

where $\psi_a(x,y)$ is a polynomial that satisfies the boundary conditions of either 1) simply supported, 2) clamped or 3) free conditions and c_a 's are unknown coefficients to be determined. By substituting Eq.(16) into Eq.(13) and integrating over the entire plate after multiplying by $\psi_\beta(x,y)$, the following matrix eigenvalue problem is obtained:

$$A c = N_{ij} B^{ij} c \quad (17)$$

where

$$(a_{\alpha\beta}) = \int \int D_{ijkl} \psi_{\alpha,ijkl} \psi_{\beta,ijkl} dS \quad (18)$$

and

$$(b_{\alpha\beta}^{ij}) = \int \int \psi_{\alpha,ij} \psi_{\beta,ij} dS \quad (19)$$

where the integral range is over the entire plate surface in Eqs.(18) and (19). Symbolic algebra software, REDUCE, has been used to obtain components of Eqs.(18) and (19) for given boundary conditions starting with constructing

admissible trial functions. This task involves a formidable amount of algebra beyond regular capacities of human hands.

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It was shown in the above derivation processes that a trial function must satisfy given boundary conditions. It is possible to construct such polynomials systematically with the help of symbolic algebra software.

As an illustrative example, a rectangular composite plate, with free edge boundary conditions is selected⁴ for this study as no work has been reported for this type of boundary conditions.

A composite plate with non-dimensionalized flexural rigidities as $D_{11}=10$, $D_{12}=0.5$, $D_{16}=0$, $D_{22}=1$, $D_{26}=0$, $D_{66}=0.25$ occupying $\{(x,y), 0 < x < a, 0 < y < b\}$ is subjected to a compressional load, N_x , in the x-direction.

By applying the previously described procedure, a polynomial that satisfies the free boundary conditions on all sides of the plate is found. This polynomial was subjected to the Galerkin method to arrive at a critical buckling load. Figure 1 shows the calculated (normalized) critical buckling load, K , defined below for several aspect ratios (a/b).

$$K = \frac{N_x b^2}{\pi^2 D_{22}} \quad (20)$$

Also shown in Figure 1 are the K values obtained by this method for the plate with the same material properties but simply supported on all sides⁵ in order to show the validity of this method. For comparison purpose, solutions obtained by the classical Rayleigh method for simply supported boundary conditions are shown. As can be seen, strong correlation exists between the existing method and this method.

It is believed that if the trial function satisfies all the given boundary conditions (geometrical and natural), the solution by the Galerkin method usually yields excellent agreements with fewer terms to the true solution compared with the trial functions that satisfy only geometrical boundary conditions.

It is possible to apply the present approach to other types of problem in composites such as higher-order composite plate theory. Symbolic algebra software is now available over a wide variety of computers including Cray. It is expected that the use of symbolic algebra eases tedious and time-consuming calculations involved in the composite analyses.

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REFERENCES

1. Haji-Sheikh, A. and Mashena, M., J. Heat Transfer, 109 (1987), 551.

2. Hearn, A., REDUCE-3 User's Manual, Rand Corporation, Santa Monica, CA. (1987).
3. Nomura, S., J. Applied Mechanics, 109 (1987), 880.
4. Weber, J.A., "Buckling Analysis of Anisotropic Plates by Using a Method of Weighted Residuals and Symbolic Algebra Software," M.S. Thesis, University of Texas at Arlington, Arlington, TX. (1988).
5. J.E. Ashton, Proceedings of ASCE, Journal of the Structural Division, 95 (1968), 2119.

Solid Represents Solution of Simply Supported Plate by Rayleigh's Method

○- Integral Method Data for Simply Supported Plate

□- Integral Method Data for Free Plate

Figure 1 -- Buckling Loads for Rectangular Orthotropic Plates